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Predictive Maintenance for Wind Turbines

PMWT

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Predictive Maintenance for Wind Turbines project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Luc Thiery (e51903906@student.tuwien.ac.at) will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

For this project, we will leverage existing datasets rather than generating new data. The decision to reuse existing data stems from its availability, diversity, and cost-effectiveness. The Wind Turbine High-Speed Bearing Prognosis dataset, the Wind Turbine SCADA Dataset from Kaggle, and the NREL Wind Turbine Dataset offer comprehensive information on wind turbine operations, failures, environmental conditions, and maintenance activities. By reusing these datasets, we can access historical turbine data and failure events, facilitating a holistic analysis of predictive maintenance needs. Additionally, utilizing existing data eliminates the need for additional data collection efforts, saving time and resources for the project.

The types and formats of data to be reused in the project include CSV, MAT, and potentially other formats available in the selected datasets. These datasets contain a wide range of variables, including turbine status, power output, wind speed, temperature, humidity, failure types, and maintenance logs. The merged dataset, an intermediate goal of the project, will combine relevant variables from each dataset to enhance the predictive capabilities of the model. By incorporating diverse data sources, we aim to develop a comprehensive predictive maintenance model that considers various factors influencing turbine performance and failure.

The purpose of reusing data is to develop a predictive maintenance model for wind turbines, aligning with the project's objectives. By leveraging existing datasets, we can

identify patterns and indicators of impending turbine failures, enabling proactive maintenance scheduling and optimization of maintenance resources. The merged dataset will serve as input for model development, incorporating variables from multiple datasets to enhance predictive accuracy. Ultimately, the goal is to predict potential turbine failures before they occur, thereby minimizing downtime and maintenance costs for wind farm operators.

The expected size of the data to be reused will depend on the individual sizes of the selected datasets. The Wind Turbine High-Speed Bearing Prognosis dataset, the Wind Turbine SCADA Dataset, and the NREL Wind Turbine Dataset may vary in terms of the number of observations and variables. The merged dataset, combining variables from multiple sources, may result in a larger dataset compared to individual sources. However, the exact size will depend on the specific variables included and the extent of data preprocessing and merging performed during the project

. The origin or provenance of the reused data varies depending on the dataset. The Wind Turbine High-Speed Bearing Prognosis dataset may originate from research studies or experiments conducted by researchers or organizations involved in wind turbine maintenance and prognostics. The Wind Turbine SCADA Dataset from Kaggle may come from wind farm operators, SCADA system providers, or researchers collecting operational data from wind turbines. The NREL Wind Turbine Dataset is provided by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), which aggregates operational data from various wind turbines for research and analysis purposes.

Outside the project, the data generated or reused may be useful to various stakeholders. Wind farm operators can optimize maintenance schedules, reduce downtime, and minimize maintenance costs by utilizing the predictive maintenance model. Renewable energy researchers can gain insights into wind turbine operations and failure events, supporting research efforts in renewable energy technology and predictive maintenance methodologies. Energy policymakers can make informed decisions related to renewable energy deployment and infrastructure investments based on the analysis of wind turbine operational data. Maintenance service providers can offer proactive maintenance solutions to wind farm operators, improving service efficiency and customer satisfaction.

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Merged Final	Merged_final.csv	CSV	-	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)
R1	Wind Turbine High-Speed Bearing Prognosis	https://github.com/mathworks/WindTurbineHighSpeedBearingPrognosis-Data	no
R2	Wind Turbine Scada Dataset	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/berkerisen/wind-turbine-scada-dataset/data	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

In the context of the predictive maintenance project for wind turbines, several methods and software tools will be employed for data generation and reuse. Since the project primarily focuses on developing a predictive maintenance model using machine learning techniques, the primary method for data generation involves extracting relevant features from existing datasets and combining them to create a merged dataset. This merged dataset will serve as the input for training and evaluating the predictive maintenance model.

For data reuse, Python will be the primary programming language used throughout the project due to its versatility, extensive libraries for data manipulation and analysis, and widespread adoption in the machine learning community. Python's libraries such as pandas, NumPy, and scikit-learn will be utilized for data preprocessing, feature engineering, model development, and evaluation.

Additionally, Jupyter Notebook or similar interactive computing environments will be used for exploratory data analysis, code development, and documentation. Jupyter Notebook allows for an iterative and collaborative approach to data analysis, enabling researchers to interactively explore the data, experiment with different machine learning algorithms, and document their findings in a single document.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in README and include a timestamp of creation. Version control is automated.

At project level, we will provide a README file to ensure clarity and understanding of the data used in our research project on predictive maintenance for wind turbines. This README file will serve as a comprehensive guide to the datasets utilized, including explanations of all values and terms used. It will be structured to provide context and insight into the data at the project level, facilitating ease of understanding for researchers and stakeholders. At dataset level, each dataset used in the project will be accompanied by its own README file. These README files will contain detailed descriptions of the dataset contents, including the data sources, collection methods, and any preprocessing steps undertaken. Additionally, explanations of the data fields, values, and terminology will be provided to aid users in interpreting and analyzing the datasets effectively. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible under the GNU General Public License (GPL) version 3.0. In cases where open access is not feasible, we will provide meaningful metadata along with contact information for access requests. This approach ensures transparency and promotes data sharing while adhering to licensing requirements for data distribution.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-04-30	Github	Not yet	GPL-3.0

Repository description:

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Potential users may require various software tools to access and reuse the data, as the datasets consist of CSV, MAT, and JPG files among other formats. While specific software may be needed to open certain file types, Python offers versatility in reading and processing diverse data formats. With

Python, users can leverage libraries such as pandas for CSV files, SciPy for MAT files, and PIL or OpenCV for image files like JPG. This flexibility ensures that users can access and manipulate the data regardless of its format, facilitating its reuse for future research purposes, including the final predictive maintenance model and charts generated from the analysis.

Additionally, the entire project, including the datasets, code, and documentation, will be hosted on GitHub. GitHub provides a collaborative platform for version control, issue tracking, and project management. Users can access the project repository on GitHub, clone it locally, and utilize the provided scripts and notebooks to analyze the data, develop machine learning models, and reproduce the results. This centralized platform enhances accessibility and transparency, enabling seamless collaboration and contribution from the research community.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

To provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse, comprehensive README files will be included in the project repository on GitHub. These README files will contain information on the methodology used for data analysis, including data cleaning procedures, variable definitions, units of measurement, and any transformations applied to the data. Additionally, codebooks detailing the structure of the datasets, variable descriptions, and data sources will be provided to aid users in understanding the data and replicating the analyses. By documenting these aspects, users will have the necessary information to validate the data analysis and reuse the datasets for their own research purposes.

The data produced in the project will be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest reuse possible. The datasets will be licensed under the GNU General Public License (GPL) version 3.0, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement. This open access approach ensures that the data can be freely accessed, used, and redistributed by third parties, fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing within the research community.

Furthermore, the data produced in the project will be usable by third parties, particularly after the end of the project. By providing clear documentation, standardized formats, and open access to the data, third parties will be able to access, analyze, and build upon the datasets for future research endeavors. This long-term usability ensures that the impact of the project extends beyond its duration, contributing to ongoing research efforts in the field of predictive maintenance for wind turbines.

The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using appropriate standards, including detailed metadata describing the datasets' structure, semantics, and data usage policies. Additionally, references to the original data sources, including dataset names, authors, and sources, will be provided to ensure transparency and traceability of the data's origins.

To ensure data quality, rigorous quality assurance processes will be implemented throughout the project. This includes data validation checks to identify and correct errors or inconsistencies in the datasets, as well as verification of data completeness and accuracy. Furthermore, data cleaning procedures will be documented and applied to address any data quality issues identified during the analysis. By maintaining high data quality standards, the reliability and integrity of the research outputs will be upheld, enhancing the trustworthiness of the project findings.

In addition to addressing data-related aspects, the DMP will also consider other research outputs, such as software code, model artifacts, and documentation. Allocation of

resources, data security measures, and ethical considerations will be carefully evaluated and addressed to ensure compliance with relevant guidelines and regulations. This holistic approach to data management ensures that all aspects of the research project are conducted ethically, transparently, and in accordance with best practices.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

...

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, reuse, security, and other aspects of research data management will be carefully considered and covered as part of the Horizon Europe grant, provided they are compliant with the conditions outlined in the Grant Agreement. These costs are eligible expenses under the grant and will be allocated as necessary to ensure effective data management throughout the project lifecycle.

Responsibility for data management in the project will primarily lie with the principal investigator and the project team. The principal investigator will oversee the overall data management strategy, including the development and implementation of data management plans, allocation of resources, and coordination of data-related activities. The project team members will be responsible for executing specific tasks related to data

collection, processing, analysis, and dissemination, in accordance with the established data management protocols.

Long-term preservation of research data will be ensured through systematic archiving and preservation practices. This includes identifying and documenting the necessary resources, both financial and technical, to support data preservation efforts. The decision-making process regarding data preservation will involve input from key stakeholders, including researchers, funding agencies, and relevant institutional bodies. Criteria for determining which data to preserve and for how long will be established based on factors such as the data's scientific value, potential for reuse, legal and ethical considerations, and available resources. Regular reviews and assessments will be conducted to evaluate the continued relevance and importance of preserved data, with adjustments made as needed to maintain alignment with project objectives and community needs.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

R1 (Wind Turbine High-Speed Bearing Prognosis), R2 (Wind Turbine Scada Dataset) will be stored on GitHub. External storage will be used because personal github account

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	writing	writing	reading only

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R2	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	Github	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

